

CONCERNING ACTION SEMANTIC VERBS

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Active action in language includes actions - processes in nature and society, in the animal kingdom, according to the objective basis of semantic verbs. That is, action verbs differ from lexemes in that they belong to a different semantic field by their breadth and complexity, versatility, and the fact that they represent different actions specific to matter, depending on their material basis (object). Since the reality, the objectivity of an action, is related to its realization by a particular living being, in which it is 'materialized', then the existence of a logical subject is also measured by its absolute action. Rather, motion is the living form of matter.

Key words:*semantic field, active action, dynamic movement, horizontal, vertical, rotation, oscillation, expressive, resultant execution.*

The causative thing in objective existence is that verbs that express different active actions specific to objects, individuals, and animals are often used in speech and have a complex semantic structure. The common semantics of the semantics of action verbs is 'active action', which unites the verbs into one macrosystem (semantic field). That is, the semantic field of verbs is formed on the basis of the "active action" sema of the common sema character.

The unifying sema is also initially part of the common sema and is separated as a result of the analysis. When one is compared to the other, the meaning of action verbs is broadly common to the common sema, and is considered an important sema inherent in action verbs within languages. The unifying sema is similar to the common sema, but it is a sema that always occurs after the common sema, which is defined, narrowing the scope of the common sema expression. Hence, this or that LSG of action verbs is formed on the basis of the unifying sema.

It is well known that any commonality arises from specificity, from individuality, from their logical internal connection, and is manifested through specificity, depending on the situation. So, the movement is seen as a generality, they have relative independence, individuality. Action is a semaphore that ensures the independence of common semantic verbs and causes them to be interpreted as a unit of language and speech. It is considered the main, central sema, combining other important and insignificant semas around itself in speech.

They are stored as an opportunity that is ready to emerge in a particular speech situation. It turns out that in the speech context, the differentiating sema becomes the 'living' unit, the method, the essential component, i.e. the companion, of the unifying sema.

Based on our observations in the explanatory dictionaries of Uzbek and English languages and verbs used in oral speech, we initially divided the verbs into the following groups according to their meaning:

Action verbs. In these LSG "dynamic (active) movement" is a common sema, "horizontal", "vertical", "rotation", "oscillation", "signaling the transition of an object from a vertical to a horizontal position", "breathing and sound (sound)", fragments of meaning such as "expressive", "resultant execution", "resultant abstract execution", and "actions in the oral cavity" are the unifying sema. The action of the logical subject, which is manifested in the verbs of action in language, occurs in the above forms. Hence, the complex nature of the semantics of verbs, which reflect different actions in an objective being, logically leads to a semantic grouping of action verbs consisting of the nine views noted.

USED LITERATURE:

1. Nida E.A. Analysis of meaning and dectionaru meaning // International Journal of American Linguistics. V.24.№4. 1958.-P. 279-292.
2. **Katz J. and Fodor J.** The structure of a semantic theory // Language.39,1963.
3. Расулов Р. Ўзбек тилидаги ҳолат феъллари ва уларнинг облигатор валентликлари. Т., 1989.
4. Расулов Р.Ў., Нарзиева Н Лексикологияни ўрганиш. - Тошкент: Ўқитувчи, 1999
5. Ҳожиев А. Тилшунослик терминларининг изоҳли луғати. –Тошкент: Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси. 2002.
6. Нейматов Ҳ., Расулов Р. Ўзбек тили систем лексикологияси асослари. Т., “Ўқитувчи”, 1995.
7. Гулига Е.В., Шендельс Е.И. О компонентном анализе значимых единиц языка// Принципы и методы семантических исследований. - М., 1976.